

Phytochemical screening and Antioxidant Activity Evaluation of Blepheris Edulis

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Abstract: Herbal medicines have gained significant attention for their potential therapeutic benefits, driven by the presence of bioactive phytochemicals that contribute to various pharmacological activities. Phytochemicals, such as flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and phenolic compounds, are commonly found in a wide range of medicinal plants, offering significant antioxidant properties. These natural compounds play a crucial role in scavenging free radicals, thereby mitigating oxidative stress, which is implicated in the development of various chronic diseases. The aim of present study is to evaluate the phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity of Blepheris Edulis extract.

Key-words: Herbal medicine, Phytochemical screening, Antioxidant Activity, Blepheris Edulis

Introduction: Herbal medicine has been an integral part of traditional healing systems across various cultures for centuries. The increasing interest in plant-based remedies is driven by the potential health benefits they offer, particularly in disease prevention and management [1]. One of the primary reasons for the therapeutic effectiveness of herbal medicine is the presence of bioactive compounds known as phytochemicals. These naturally occurring substances, including flavonoids, phenolics, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins, exhibit significant pharmacological properties, making them valuable in the development of modern pharmaceuticals [2]. The focus on phytochemical analysis has gained prominence in recent years due to its role in identifying and quantifying these

bioactive constituents. Understanding the phytochemical profile of herbs is essential for determining their therapeutic efficacy and potential applications in treating various ailments. Furthermore, the standardization of herbal formulations based on their phytochemical constituents ensures consistency, safety, and potency in herbal medicine [3]. Among the numerous pharmacological properties of phytochemicals, their antioxidant activity is of particular interest. Oxidative stress, caused by an imbalance between free radicals and antioxidants in the body, is implicated in various chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, neurodegenerative conditions, and cancer [4]. Antioxidants play a crucial role in neutralizing free radicals, thereby reducing cellular damage and preventing disease progression. Many medicinal plants have been identified as rich sources of antioxidants, with polyphenols, flavonoids, and carotenoids being the key parameters [5]. The assessment of antioxidant activity in herbal medicine involves various methods. The integration of phytochemical analysis with antioxidant activity evaluation enhances our understanding of the medicinal properties of plants. It also contributes to the development of novel herbal formulations with improved efficacy and stability [6]. However, challenges such as variations in plant composition due to environmental factors, extraction methods, and processing techniques must be addressed to ensure reproducibility and reliability in herbal medicine research. Further studies on the synergistic interactions of phytochemicals and their mechanisms of action will help in optimizing their therapeutic potential. As the demand for natural remedies continues to grow, scientific validation of herbal medicine through phytochemical and antioxidant research remains a priority [7]. A multidisciplinary approach combining traditional knowledge with modern analytical techniques is essential for establishing the safety, efficacy, and standardization of herbal products. By deepening our understanding of the phytochemical composition and antioxidant properties of medicinal plants, we can pave the way for the development of effective plant-based therapies for various health conditions. Green plants synthesize and preserve a variety of biochemical products, many of which are extractable and used as chemical feed stocks or as a raw material for various scientific investigations. The aim of present study is to evaluate the phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity of *Blepharis Edulis* extract.

Material And Methods

Collection and identification of plant material: The subject of phytochemistry or plant chemistry has developed in recent years as a distinct discipline, somewhere in between natural product organic chemistry and plant biochemistry and is closely related to both. It is concerned with the enormous variety of organic substances that are elaborated and accumulated by plants and deals with the chemical structures of these substances, their biosynthesis, turnover and metabolism, natural distribution and biological function. *Blepharis edulis* seeds purchased from local market Bhopal. Plant material was identified and authenticated by botanist. The plant materials were dried in shade, powdered moderately and pass through sieve No. 10.

Extraction of plant material (*Blepharis Edulis*): The crude plant material was often subjected to the selective extraction comprised of treating the moderately coarse powder of plant material with non-polar solvent in succession to extract various plant constituents according to their solubility. The powdered *Blepharis edulis* seeds (200 gm) were successively extracted in a soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (60-80°C), Ethyl acetate and methanol. The extract obtained with each solvent was weighed to a constant weight and percentage w/w yield was calculated. Successive solvent extracts (Petroleum ether, Ethyl acetate and methanol) were subjected for qualitative analysis.

Phytochemical Test: All extracts were subject to various qualitative analysis to detect the presence of plant constituents such as Alkaloids, Glycosides, Saponins, Carbohydrates, Phytosterols, Tannins and phenolic compounds (flavonoids), Proteins and free amino acids.

Anti-oxidant Activity: Antioxidants may be defined as any substance, when present at low concentration compared with those of an oxidizable substrate, significantly delays or prevents oxidation of that substrate in a chain reaction. Antioxidant actions might be exerted by inhibiting generation of reactive oxygen species and reactive nitrogen species or by directly scavenging free radical or by raising the levels of endogenous antioxidant enzymes by up regulating expression of the genes encoding superoxide dismutase, catalase or glutathione peroxidase. For the assessment of free radical scavenging activity,

the extracts of selected plants were dissolved in 5% DMSO. DPPH, Nitric oxide, hydroxyl radical, superoxide radical methods were carried in the present study.

Chemicals and plant extract: 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH), DMSO, Ascorbic acid Sodium nitro prusside, Griess reagent (1%w/v sulphanilamide, 2% w/v H₃PO₄ and N-(1-naphthyl) ethylene diamine di hydrochloride), Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) Thiobarbituric acid Sodium phosphate buffer, 1mM ferric chloride Nitro blue tetrazolium Phenazene methosulphate, Nicotinamide adenine phosphate di nucleotide

Table 1: Sample code for Anti-oxidant Activity

S No.	Sample	Description
1	PBE	Petroleum ether extracts of <i>blepharis edulis</i> seeds
2	EBE	Ethyl acetate extract of <i>blepharis edulis</i> seeds
3	MBE	Methanol extract of <i>blepharis edulis</i> seeds

Determination of DPPH radical scavenging activity of extracts: The free radical scavenging activity of the extracts were evaluated using 1,1 diphenyl-2- picryl hydrazyl (DPPH). In its radical form, DPPH absorbs at 517nm, but upon reduction by an antioxidant or a radical species, the absorption decreases. 1ml of 0.25mM solution of DPPH in DMSO was added to the different concentrations of selected plant extracts which were dissolved in DMSO (100- 500µg/ml). After 30 min, the absorbance was measured at 517nm by UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-Vis 1800). All the test analysis were run in triplicate and averaged. Lower absorbance of reaction mixture indicates higher free radical scavenging activity. Ascorbic was used as a positive control. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard. The extracts were added with three ml of DPPH (0.5 mM/ L) in methanol. The absorbance was recorded at 517 nm after 30 minutes of incubation at 37°C. The percentage of scavenging activity was calculated using following formula,

$$\% \text{ of inhibition} = (A_1 - A_2)/A_1 \times 100$$

Where, A₁ = Absorbance of DPPH

A2 = Absorbance of the reaction mixture with extract (DPPH with Sample)

Determination of Nitric Oxide (NO) radical scavenging activity of extracts: Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity the method used was based on the standard methods with some modification. Nitric oxide (NO) was generated from sodium nitro prusside (SNP) and was measured by the griess reagent (1% w/v sulfanilamide, 2%w/v H₃PO₃ and 0.1% w/v N-(1-Naphthyl) ethylene diamine dihydrochloride). SNP in aqueous solution at physiological PH spontaneously generates NO, which interacts with oxygen to produce nitrite ions that can be estimated by the use of griess reagent. Scavengers of NO compete with oxygen leading to reduced production of NO. SNP (1ml of mM) was mixed with 1ml of selected plants extracts in different concentrations in (Di methyl sulphoxide) DMSO. The mixture was incubated at 25°C for 180 minutes. To 1ml of the incubated solution, 1ml of griess reagent was added. The absorbance of the chromophores formed during the diazotization of nitrite with sulphanilamide and subsequent coupling with N-(1-naphthyl) ethylene diamine dihydrochloride was read at 546nm by UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-Vis1800). All the test analysis were run in triplicate and averaged. Lower absorbance of reaction mixture indicates higher free radical scavenging activity. Ascorbic was used as a positive control. The percentage inhibition was calculated by

Percentage of Nitric oxide scavenged = $[(A_0 - A_1)/A_0] \times 100$,

Where A₀ = Absorbance of the control, and

A₁ = Absorbance of the extract/ standard.

Phytochemical screening and Pharmacological evaluation of *Blepharis Edulis* for Antioxidant Activity.

Determination of hydroxyl radical scavenging activity: Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity was determined by the method of (Halliwell et al 1995) based on the ability to compete with deoxyribose for hydroxyl radical. Hydroxyl radical produced by the reduction of H₂O₂ by iron in the presence of ascorbic acid degrade deoxyribose to form products, which on heating with 2-thiobarbuturic acid (TBA) for a pink coloured chromogen. The reaction mixture, of a final volume of 1ml, containing 0.4ml of 20mM

sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), 0.1ml of 100-500 µg/ml of selected plant extracts in DMSO, 0.1ml of 60mM deoxyribose, 0.1 ml of 10mM H₂O₂, 0.1 ml of 1mM ferric chloride, 0.1 ml of 1Mm Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) and 0.1ml of 2mM 1-ascorbic acid, was incubated at 37°C for 1 h. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 1 ml of 17mM TBA and 1ml of 17Mm trichloro acetic acid (TCA). The mixture was boiled for 15 min, cooled in ice and the absorbance was measured at 532nm by UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-Vis 1800). All the test analysis were run in triplicate and averaged. L-Ascorbic acid was used as a positive control. The hydroxyl radical scavenging of the extract was reported as the percentage of inhibition of the deoxyribose degradation and was calculated according to the following equation

Calculation of % Inhibition:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = [(A_0 - A_T) / A_0] * 100$$

Where A₀ = Absorbance of the control, and

A_T = Absorbance of the extract/ standard.

Determination of super oxide radical scavenging activity: Super oxide anion derived from dissolved oxygen by a PMS-NADH coupling reaction reduces nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT), which forms a violet coloured complex.

A decrease in colour after addition of the antioxidant is a measure of its super oxide scavenging agent¹⁴. The experiment, the super oxide radicals were generated in 3 ml of Tris-HCL buffer (16Mm pH 8) containing 1 ml of NBT (50 µM), 1 ml NADH (78 µM) and test solution of selected plant extracts, (100-500 µg/ml) to the above reaction mixture, 1 ml PMS solution (10 µ M) was added and incubated at 25°C for 5 min. The absorbance was read at 560nm (Shimadzu UV-Vis 1800) against blank sample. Decrease in absorbance of the reaction mixture incubated increases super oxide anion scavenging activity. All the test analysis were run in triplicate and averaged. L-ascorbic acid was used as a positive control.

The % inhibition of super oxide anion generated was calculated using the following equation

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = [(A_0 - A_T) / A_0] * 100$$

Where A₀ = Absorbance of the control, and A_T = Absorbance of test extract/ standard.

Results

Extraction of plant material: The extraction of drug signifies a solid from solid separation, as solid components must be extracted from a solid substance. This type of extraction is generally performed before any separation processing and should be differentiated from solid liquid extraction where the solid drug is extracted with a liquid medium. The liquid extraction is one in which any of the two liquids that are not miscible includes the substance to be extracted. Extractive values are useful for the evaluation of nature of the active phytoconstituents present in the drug especially when the constituents of a drug cannot be readily estimated by any other means. The percentage yield of extract was calculated with reference to the air-dried drug used for the study. The percentage yield of the extracts was tabulated below.

Table 2: Percentage yield of various extracts of *Blepharis edulis* seeds

Solvents used for extraction	% yield (w/w)
Petroleum ether	2.98
Ethyl acetate	6.54
Methanol	14.23

Phytochemical screening: Phytochemical screening provides an idea about the preliminary chemical composition of the extracts. The chemical tests were performed as per the standard procedures. Methanol extracts of *Blepharis edulis* seed found containing maximum number of secondary metabolites in comparison to other extracts. Various tests were performed to detect presence of various primary as well as secondary chemical constituents in the extract of *Blepharis edulis* seed.

Table 3: Preliminary phytochemical screening *Blepharis edulis* seeds extract

S. No.	Phytochemical Tests	Petroleum ether extracts (PBE)	Ethyl acetate extract (EBE)	Methanol extract (MBE)
1	Carbohydrates	-	-	+
2	Proteins And Amino Acids	-	-	+
3	Acidic Compounds	-	-	-
4	Mucilage	-	-	+
5	Fixed Oil	-	-	-
6	Alkaloids	-	-	-
7	Glycosides	-	-	+
8	Sterols And Steroids	+	-	-
9	Anthraquinones	-	-	+
10	Flavonoids	-	-	+
11	Phenolic Compounds	-	-	+
12	Terpenoids	+	+	-
13	Saponins	-	-	-

Anti-oxidant Activity: Analysis of the free radical scavenging activities of the *Blepharis edulis* seed extracts revealed a concentration dependent free radical scavenging activity resulting from reduction of DPPH, nitric oxide radical to non-radical form. The scavenging activity of Ascorbic acid, a known antioxidant used as positive control, was however higher.

DPPH radical scavenging activity: DPPH radical is considered to be a model for a lipophilic radical. A chain in lipophilic radicals was initiated by the lipid autoxidation. DPPH is a stable free radical at room temperature and accepts an electron or hydrogen radical to become a stable diamagnetic molecule. The reduction capacity of DPPH was

determined by the decrease in its absorbance at 517 nm, which is induced by antioxidant. Positive DPPH test suggests that the samples were free radical scavengers. The scavenging effect of l-Ascorbic acid, and plant extracts increased gradually with increase in concentration. Percentage Inhibition of in vitro anti-oxidant result of various *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts by DPPH Method and ascorbic acid as standard at various concentrations. In case of *Blepharis edulis* extracts the methanol, extract was found to have greater reduction potential than other extracts.

Table 4: Effect of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on DPPH radical scavenging model

Concentration	100 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	52.23	75.27	91.94
PBE	8.47	20.54	36.54
EBE	17.87	24.87	59.87
MBE	47.87	62.65	79.12

Figure 1: Effect of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on DPPH radical scavenging model

Nitric Oxide (NO) radical scavenging activity of extract: Nitric oxide plays an important role in various types of inflammatory processes in the body

Table 5: Effect of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on Nitric oxide radical scavenging model

Concentration	100 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	55.27	74.18	94.13
PBE	14.75	18.48	27.42
EBE	31.63	46.12	60.36
MBE	44.29	62.14	72.94

Figure 2: Effect of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on Nitric oxide radical scavenging model

. In the present study the *Blepharis edulis* seeds checked for its inhibitory effect on Nitric oxide production. Nitric oxide radical generated for sodium nitroprusside at physiological

pH was found to be inhibited by the extracts. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of nitric oxide radical scavenging activity compared to other extract. Results revealed that all the tested extracts showed the percentage of inhibition in a dose dependent manner. The inhibitory effect of *Blepharis edulis* seed extracts on Nitric oxide radical scavenging model were revealed that methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seed at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of nitric oxide radical scavenging activity compared to other extract.

Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of extracts: The hydroxyl radical is an extremely reactive free radical formed in biological systems and has been implicated as a highly damaging species in free radical pathology, capable of damaging almost every molecule found in living cells. This radical has the capacity to join nucleotides in DNA and cause strand breakage, which contributes to carcinogenesis, mutagenesis and cytotoxicity. Hydroxyl radical scavenging capacity of an extract is directly related to its antioxidant activity.

Table 6: Effect of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on Hydroxyl radical scavenging model

Concentration	100 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	50.27	70.18	91.28
PBE	14.63	20.28	24.24
EBE	20.41	37.26	60.37
MBE	35.38	49.24	72.26

The highly reactive hydroxyl radicals can cause oxidative damage to DNA, lipids and proteins. The effect of the selected plant extracts were assessed by means of the iron (II)-dependent DNA damage assay. The fentone reaction generated hydroxyl radicals (OH) which degrade DNA deoxy ribose, using Fe²⁺ salts as an important catalytic component. Oxygen radicals may attack DNA either at the sugar or the base, giving rise to a large

number of products. All the results showed hydroxyl radical scavenging activity in a dose dependent manner. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of hydroxyl radical scavenging activity compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract.

Figure 3: Effect of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on Hydroxyl radical scavenging model

All the results showed hydroxyl radical scavenging activity in a dose dependent manner. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of hydroxyl radical scavenging activity compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract.

Super oxide radical scavenging activity of extracts: Superoxide is a reactive oxygen species, which can cause damage to the cells and DNA leading to various diseases. It was therefore proposed to measure the comparative interceptive ability of the antioxidant extracts to scavenge the superoxide radical. Several In vitro methods are available for generation of super oxide radicals. In the present study the superoxide radicals were generated by auto-oxidation of hydroxylamine in the presence of NBT (Nitro blue tetrazolium). The reduction of NBT in presence of antioxidants was measured. The decrease of absorbance at 560 nm with antioxidants thus indicates the consumption of

superoxide anion in the reaction mixture. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of superoxide radical activity scavenging compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract.

Table 7: Results of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on super oxide radical scavenging activity

Concentration	100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Ascorbic acid	34.17	53.87	71.21
PBE	12.74	19.54	30.47
EBE	22.54	38.45	55.75
MBE	37.57	50.54	68.14

Figure 4: Results of *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts on super oxide radical scavenging activity

From this work we conclude that all the extracts were exhibiting significant scavenging activity towards 1, 1-di phenyl picryl hydrazyl, Nitric oxide, Hydroxyl, Super oxide radicals. The activity was found to be concentration dependent. In DPPH model the free radical scavenging capacity was found to be highly significant when compare other three

models. Methanol extract was found to have high scavenging activity than Ethyl acetate and petroleum ether extracts. Scavenging activity of methanol extracts may be due to presence of the flavonoids and phenolic.

Discussion

DPPH radical is considered to be a model for a lipophilic radical. A chain in lipophilic radicals was initiated by the lipid autoxidation. DPPH is a stable free radical at room temperature and accepts an electron or hydrogen radical to become a stable diamagnetic molecule. The reduction capacity of DPPH was determined by the decrease in its absorbance at 517 nm, which is induced by antioxidant. Positive DPPH test suggests that the samples were free radical scavengers. The scavenging effect of l-Ascorbic acid, and plant extracts increased gradually with increase in concentration. Percentage Inhibition of in vitro anti-oxidant result of various *Blepharis edulis* seeds extracts by DPPH Method and ascorbic acid as standard at various concentrations. In case of *Blepharis edulis* leaves extracts the methanol extract were found to have greater reduction potential than other extracts. Nitric oxide plays an important role in various types of inflammatory processes in the body. In the present study the fruit extracts of selected of *Blepharis edulis* checked for its inhibitory effect on Nitric oxide production. Nitric oxide radical generated for sodium nitroprusside at physiological pH was found to be inhibited by the extracts. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of nitric oxide radical scavenging activity compared to other extract. Results revealed that all the tested extracts showed the percentage of inhibition in a dose dependent manner. The inhibitory effect of *Blepharis edulis* seed extracts on Nitric oxide radical scavenging model were revealed that methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seed at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of nitric oxide radical scavenging activity compared to other extract. The hydroxyl radical is an extremely reactive free radical formed in biological systems and has been implicated as a highly damaging species in free radical pathology, capable of damaging almost every molecule found in living cells. This radical has the capacity to join nucleotides in DNA and cause strand breakage, which contributes to carcinogenesis, mutagenesis and cytotoxicity. Hydroxyl radical scavenging capacity of an extract is directly related to its antioxidant activity. The highly reactive hydroxyl radicals can cause oxidative damage to DNA,

lipids and proteins. The effect of the selected plant extracts were assessed by means of the iron (II)- dependent DNA damage assay. The fentone reaction generated hydroxyl radicals (OH) which degrade DNA deoxy ribose, using Fe 2+ salts as an important catalytic component. Oxygen radicals may attack DNA either at the sugar or the base, giving rise to a large number of products. All the results showed hydroxyl radical scavenging activity in a dose dependent manner. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of hydroxyl radical scavenging activity compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract. All the results showed hydroxyl radical scavenging activity in a dose dependent manner. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of hydroxyl radical scavenging activity compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract.

Superoxide is a reactive oxygen species, which can cause damage to the cells and DNA leading to various diseases. It was therefore proposed to measure the comparative interceptive ability of the antioxidant extracts to scavenge the superoxide radical. Several In vitro methods are available for generation of super oxide radicals. In the present study the superoxide radicals were generated by auto-oxidation of hydroxylamine in the presence of NBT (Nitro blue tetrazolium). The reduction of NBT in presence of antioxidants was measured. The decrease of absorbance at 560 nm with antioxidants thus indicates the consumption of superoxide anion in the reaction mixture. The methanol extract of *Blepharis edulis* seeds at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of superoxide radical activity scavenging compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract. From this work we conclude that all the extracts were exhibiting significant scavenging activity towards 1, 1-di phenyl picryl hydrazyl, Nitric oxide, Hydroxyl, Super oxide radicals. The activity was found to be concentration dependent. In DPPH model the free radical scavenging capacity was found to be highly significant when compare other three models.

Conclusion:

Phytochemical screening provides an idea about the preliminary chemical composition of the extracts. The chemical tests were performed as per the standard procedures. Methanol

extracts of *Blepharis edulis* seed found containing maximum number of secondary metabolites in comparison to other extracts. Various tests were performed to detect presence of various primary as well as secondary chemical constituents in the extract of *Blepharis edulis* seed. Analysis of the free radical scavenging activities of the *Blepharis edulis* seed extracts revealed a concentration dependent free radical scavenging activity resulting from reduction of DPPH, nitric oxide radical to non-radical form. The scavenging activity of Ascorbic acid, a known antioxidant used as positive control, was however higher.

References

1. Kurata JH, Nogawa AN. Meta-analysis of risk factors for peptic ulcer. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, Helicobacter pylori, and smoking. *Journal of Clinical Gastroenterology*, 1997, 24, 2-17.
2. Nilsson C, Sillen A, Eriksson L, Strand ML, Enroth H, Normark S, Falk P, Engstrand L. Correlation between cag pathogenicity island composition and Helicobacter pylori-associated gastroduodenal disease. *Infection and Immunity*, 2003, 71, 6573- 6581.
3. Wallace JL, Granger DN. Pathogenesis of NSAID gastropathy: are neutrophils the culprits? *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, 1992; 13, 129-131.
4. Wolfe MM, Sachs G. Acid suppression: optimizing therapy for gastroduodenal ulcer healing, gastroesophageal reflux disease, and stress-related erosive syndrome. *Gastroenterology*, 2000; 118, S9-S31.
5. Dajani, E.; Trotman, B. Drugs for treatment of peptic ulcers. *J. Assoc. Acad. Minority Physic. Official Publ. Asso. Acad. Minority Physic.* 1992, 3, 78–88.
6. De Barros, M.; da Silva, L.M.; Boeing, T.; Somensi, L.B.; Cury, B.J.; Burci, L.D.; Santin, J.R.; de Andrade, S.F.; Delle Monache, F.; Cechinel, V. Pharmacological reports about gastroprotective effects of methanolic extract from leaves of *Solidago chilensis* (Brazilian arnica) and its components quercitrin and afzelin in rodents. *N-S Arch. Pharmacol.* 2016, 389, 403–417.

7. Graham, D.Y. Changing patterns of peptic ulcer, gastroesophageal reflux disease and *Helicobacter pylori*: A unifying hypothesis. *Eur. J. Gastroen. Hepat.* 2003, 15, 571–572.
8. Jamal A, Siddiqui A, Tajuddin Jafri MA. 2006. A review on gastric ulcer remedies used in Unani System of Medicine. *Nat Prod Radiance.* 5:153–159.
9. Ohno T, Hattori Y, Komine R, Ae T, Mizuguchi S, Arai K, Saeki T, Suzuki T, Hosono K, Hayashi I, et al. 2008. Roles of calcitonin gene-related peptide in maintenance of gastric mucosal integrity and in enhancement of ulcer healing and angiogenesis. *Gastroenterology.* 134:215–225.
10. Levenstein, S.; Rosenstock, S.; Jacobsen, R.K.; Jorgensen, T. Psychological stress increases risk for peptic ulcer, regardless of *Helicobacter pylori* infection or use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. *Clin. Gastroen. Hepatol.* 2015, 13, 498–506.e491.
11. Zhang, X.-Y.; Zhang, P.-Y.; Aboul-Soud, M.A. From inflammation to gastric cancer: Role of *Helicobacter pylori*. *Oncol. lett.* 2017, 13, 543–548.
12. Kuruvilla A. (2002) Herbal formulations as pharmacotherapeutic agents. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 40, 7-11.
13. Gracioso JS, Hiruma-Lima CA, Souza Brito AR. (2000) Antiulcerogenic effect of a hydroalcoholic extract and its organic fractions of *Neurolaena lobata* (L.) R.Br. *Phytomedicine*, 7, 283-289.
14. Hiruma-Lima CA, Gracioso JS, Bighetti EJ, Grassi-Kassisse DM, Nunes DS, Brito AR. (2002) Effect of essential oil obtained from *Croton cajucara* Benth. on gastric ulcer healing and protective factors of the gastric mucosa. *Phytomedicine*, 9, 523-529.
15. M. Walsh, S. Fais, E.P. Spugnini, S. Harguindey, T.A. Izneid, L. Scacco, P. Williams, C. Allegrucci, C. Rauch, Z. Omran Proton pump inhibitors for the treatment of cancer in companion animals *J. Exp. Clin. Cancer Res.*, 34 (1) (2015), 1-9